

**METHODS FOR PRODUCING DETERGENT-DISPERSE
ADDITIVES AND THEIR APPLICATION IN IMPROVING THE
PROPERTIES OF DIESEL FUEL**

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Currently, natural gas and oil are the main energy sources of strategic importance in the world. The products obtained on the basis of their processing are widely used in all industries, transport, energy, agriculture and everyday life. For this reason, the use of energy-efficient technologies in the initial processing of hydrocarbon raw materials is an urgent problem.

In our country, scientific research works aimed at raising the production to a new level, modernizing and diversifying it, introducing innovative technologies, increasing the volume and quality of the produced products and expanding their types are being carried out in our country [1,2] .

Washing-dispersing compounds designed to ensure the service life of diesel fuel equipment have been widely used for more than 30 years. This is explained by the washing effect of the particles, washing and cleaning of fuel equipment from soot and other additives [3,4,5].

In recent years, it is recommended to use composite additives containing cyclic amines and their derivatives as washing-dispersing additives for diesel fuels. One of the main properties of cyclic amine derivatives that can be used in detergent dispersants for diesel fuels is their thermal stability. As components in these compositions, tetrahydropyrimidine (1); imidazoline (2); it is recommended to use piperazine (3) derivatives.

Here - R1, R2, R3, R4, R5 - hydrocarbon substituents S1 - S20.

Nowadays, compositions containing various surfactants such as amines, amides, imides, amidines and oxygenated (glycols, polyglycols, amine alcohols and their esters, ionic complexes with organic acids) substances are widely used abroad.

The main requirements for detergent dispersants are as follows:

1. The additive should be ash-free or low-ash and dissolve well in diesel fuel, and one of the elements of its structure should be a hydrocarbon radical.
2. The additive must have the properties of a surfactant (SFM), so it must contain at least one polar (amine, amide, carboxyl or other) group.
3. The additive must be thermally stable and not decompose up to 220-225 °C, therefore it is recommended to include derivatives of cyclic amines in its composition.

Experimental data obtained by special methods are of great importance in the development of additives [6,7,8]. A full description of these methods can be found in the Compilation of Qualified Methods for the Evaluation of Diesel Fuels.

The available methods of evaluating the activity of detergent dispersants can be divided into two groups:

1. A method of studying the dispersing and stabilizing properties of the particles, their effect on their stability against model fuel (individual hydrocarbons, binary mixture of hydrocarbons) or artificially prepared suspensions in real fuel of known composition (composite, deposits in real fuels).

The dispersing properties of the particles, the change in the dispersion of the particles in the presence of the particles are evaluated by the optical or sedimentation method, and the stabilizing properties are determined by the change in the stability of the dispersion obtained over time. The solubilizing properties of the particles are evaluated by their ability to transfer the additives in the model fuel into a colloidal solution.

2. The method of evaluation of the influence of the particles on the formation of deposits when heating real fuels to a temperature of 220-225 °C. This method is a method for evaluating the thermal stability of particulate fuels in LSART and TSRT-2 equipment under static conditions, as well as a method for thermal evaluation of particulate fuels in DTS-1 and DTS-2 equipment under dynamic conditions.

Dynamic methods can include a method based on the starting temperature of the resinization process of diesel injectors, in which real fuel with and without a plug heated by electric current passes between the nozzles at a temperature of 120-220 °C for 5 hours. The rating is based on the thickness of the varnish on the needles of the sprayers and the force of the exit of the needle from the body of the sprayer.

Naturally, these methods allow to obtain only approximately the efficiency of differentiation of detergent dispersant additives for diesel fuels. At the moment, there is a need to develop a complex of laboratory methods for the purpose of

26.3 g of morpholine was added dropwise to it, and the temperature of the reaction mixture was maintained at 30-35°C by removing excess heat through an ice container. A white powdery precipitate formed. After the morpholine was completely reacted, the reaction mixture was stirred for another 10-15 min. After that, the temperature was lowered to 5-7 °C. The ionic complex of morpholine with valerian acid was filtered, washed three times in heptane and dried under vacuum at 20°C. Yield 42.1 g. (82.3%). Liquefaction temperature is 35°C.

2. Obtaining the ionic complex of benzoic acid and morpholine was carried out as follows:

A solution of 36.6 g (0.3 M) benzoic acid in 150 mL of chloroform was poured into a 500 mL three-necked flask equipped with a stirrer, thermometer, reflux condenser, and dropping funnel with constant vigorous stirring. The solution was heated to a temperature of 60-65°C and 26.3 g of morpholine was added dropwise. Due to the ionic complex formed, which is poorly soluble in chloroform, the reaction mixture immediately curdles. After complete addition of morpholine, the reaction mixture was stirred at 60-65°C for 2 hours. After that, the temperature was lowered to room temperature, and the formed crystals were filtered, washed twice with chloroform and dried under vacuum at room temperature. The yield is 56.1 g. (89.3%). The melting temperature is 127-128 °C.

3. Synthesis of amides based on caproic acid and diethylamine:

124 g (1.0 M) meta-toluic acid was added to a 250 mL four-necked flask equipped with a stirrer, thermometer, reflux condenser, and dropping funnel. Then it was heated to a temperature of 115°C. Then, with vigorous mixing, 87 g. (1.0 M) of morpholine was added dropwise, and the temperature was maintained at 115-120°C. After complete incorporation of the amine, the reaction mixture was heated to 145-155°C and stirred at this temperature for 20-25 min. After that, the temperature was reduced to room temperature and the reaction mixture was added to an equal amount of benzene and washed with water and 5% KON. After recrystallization in heptane, a white crystalline substance was obtained, melting point 54°C, boiling point 191-194°C at 7 mm wire. Product yield is 168.8g. (80.3%).

Complex salts were obtained in two stages: in the first stage - the complex was synthesized, and in the second stage - the water molecule was separated from the ionic complex molecule under the influence of temperature, in which the group characteristic of amides - C(O)N·R₂ – created.

With all the used acids, morpholine reacts very rapidly even at room

temperature. In interaction with synthetic fatty acids, the activity of amines decreases according to the following order, depending on the base constant:

piperidine>diethanolamine>diethylamine>piperazine> morpholine>aniline.

It was found that the increase in the number of amino groups in the molecule of the initial amine leads to deterioration of the functional properties and thermal stability of amines of carboxylic acids obtained on their basis. The degree of substitution of the nitrogen atom in the amino groups, as well as the cyclic replacement of the aliphatic substituent in the molecule of the initial amine, leads to a decrease in the thermal stability and efficiency of the amides of the obtained carboxylic acids. The presence of oxygen groups (ON- and O-) in the molecule of the primary amine leads to an increase in the surface-active, dispersing and adsorption properties of the particles, as well as in terms of thermal stability, they are widely used, which means that they are also preferable in terms of detergent dispersing properties.

Thus, in order to obtain particles with high detergent-dispersing properties, it is desirable to have an oxygen-containing group in the alicyclic substituent in addition to the amino group as starting materials in the synthesis of compounds. Organic acids and derivatives of cycloamine (morpholine) meet these requirements.

5. Local injection AMG-1 consists of a mixture of 90% caproic acid amide and 10% morpholine. AMG-1 was synthesized according to the following methodology:

116 g (1.0 M) caproic acid was added to a three-necked flask equipped with a stirrer, thermometer, reflux condenser, and dropper. Then, with vigorous stirring, 87 g (1.0 M) of morpholine was added dropwise, while the temperature of the reaction mixture was maintained at 25-30 °C via an ice bath. After adding

and then washed with water and 5.0% NaOH solution. The reaction mixture was stirred in vacuo to give a colorless liquid product. Product yield 29.28 g (86.9%).

Amides synthesized in the presence of carboxylic acids and amines showed high efficiency as detergent dispersants.

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